

Towards the Educational Reconstruction of Computational Thinking and Making in Pre-Service Kindergarten Teacher Training

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Abstract. Computational Thinking (CT) and Making have been integrated into early childhood education (ECE) through various initiatives to enhance preschool students’ problem-solving and CT skills. However, for a sustainable implementation of these concepts in ECE, kindergarten teachers should receive pre-service training as part of their education. The Process Model of Educational Reconstruction provides a framework for incorporating these topics into vocational teacher training programs. This paper presents empirical findings from the perspectives of preschool students, kindergarten teachers, and vocational school teachers regarding the integration of CT and Making in ECE¹. These insights offer valuable guidance for educators and researchers seeking to embed CT and Making into early childhood curricula effectively.

Keywords: Computational Thinking · Computer Science Education · Kindergarten · Early Childhood Education · Making · Vocational Schools

1 Introduction

Interdisciplinary skills such as Computational Thinking (CT) and problem-solving have been incorporated into early childhood education (ECE) through various initiatives, including CT activities [5] and Making—such as digital fabrication or crafting with everyday materials [16, 28]. However, for a sustainable integration of CT and Making in ECE, kindergarten teacher education must adapt to prepare future educators effectively [24, 17]. Many kindergarten teachers have deliberately chosen paths outside STEM (science, technology, engineering, and mathematics) and may hold reservations about Computer Science (CS), often having no formal CS education themselves and no competences in the field [20]. To foster their interest, develop positive experiences, and build competency in CT and Making, these topics must be meaningfully incorporated into pre-service kindergarten teacher education. Only when educators themselves gain confidence and first-hand experience with CT and Making are they likely to integrate these concepts into their practice.

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The project *MakeTechEarly* addresses this gap. In the first stage, learning activities (LA) for preschool students were developed with experts in ECE [2] and piloted [3]. Next CT and Making lessons are developed with vocational teachers to sustainably integrate them into pre-service kindergarten teacher training. Given this context, it is crucial to consider vocational teachers’ perspectives when designing curricula for vocational schools in Germany (called *Fachschule*), where these kindergarten teachers receive their training. Hence, the Process Model of Educational Reconstruction for Computer Science Education (MER-CSE) [14, 12] is used to address the perspectives of vocational school teachers, kindergarten teachers, and preschool students in kindergartens. This article aims to contribute to the body of literature on CT and Making in ECE by applying the MER-CSE to the context of vocational schools in Germany that was identified as a research gap [20, 24, 17]. The core objective is to provide insights on the different perspectives students, kindergarten teachers and vocational teachers from the MER-CSE. The perspective of vocational teachers is especially relevant in this context, as they had no formal CS education (role of the learner and teacher) and have to foster kindergarten teachers content knowledge as well as pedagogical content knowledge in CT and Making (double layered teaching practice). The next sections briefly summarize the MER-CSE and methodology. Afterwards the findings are presented. The paper ends with a discussion, including limitations and conclusions for research and practice on CT and Making in ECE.

2 Background

Lesson plans and research projects that integrate emerging technologies or concepts not yet included in curricula can be developed using the MER-CSE [14, 12]. This research framework was successfully used for structuring several research projects in the past [14]. This model, based on the work of Diethelm et al. [12], begins by examining multiple perspectives: those of teachers and students, societal demands, and the structure of the scientific content. A key step in this process is analysing the underlying elementary ideas within the given context—in this case, CT and Making in ECE—to determine the fundamental ideas that should be addressed (key question: *What* content should we teach?) [22]. The insights gained from this analysis help clarify the core scientific concepts and identify how they can be meaningfully integrated into existing curricula. The underlying social perspective—such as social participation, gender equality, and future skills [19]—helps answer the question: *Why* should we engage with this content? [22]. Based on the constructivist approach [6], which is also a key approach in ECE [7], students’ perspectives, prior knowledge, and conceptualizations of CT and Making should be considered and built upon. As outlined in the motivation, teachers’ perspectives (especially if they have little prior knowledge in the field) are also crucial. They can provide initial insights into *how* they would teach the new content and what they already know about it. The next phases are the selection of CS concepts, context and afterwards phenomena and finally the development and implementation of the lessons including teaching

guidelines and learning environments. Thus, the main didactical questions of CS [22] are effectively addressed by MER-CSE. The hole model complemented by the perspective of the kindergarten teachers due to the double-layered teaching practice (vocational teachers, kindergarten teachers, and preschool students) is illustrated in Figure 1.

Fig. 1. Visualization of the MER-CSE [14, 12] adapted from [14] and complemented by the perspectives of kindergarten teachers

Science content structure. According to Ebner et al. [13], *Making* can be defined as creating things by oneself using manual and digital creative designs. Making can incorporate aspects of CT, such as sketching a design, following step-by-step instructions, creating and communicating instructions, and identifying mistakes during the creation process [26]. Furthermore, design thinking—an iterative process that involves identifying goals, understanding needs, and developing solutions—can be taught through Making [15]. Complemented to some concepts, practices and perspectives that are considered by the CT rubric [29] design thinking and iteratively crafting products by using creativity connecting various materials (hardware) making choices of conduct as well as collaborating with other students and communicating the results of decisions are concepts and perspectives that can be considered when integrating Making into ECE [26, 7, 13]. Several studies on CT in ECE have been conducted, according to the literature review of Bati [5]. However, the definitions of CT vary depending on the context [10]. In this article, we define CT according to Wing as "the thought processes involved in formulating a problem and expressing its solution(s) in such a way that a computer—human or machine—can effectively carry out" ([27], p. 8). The machine or robot is in the context of ECE an age-appropriate education robot (e. g. the Bee-Bot) [5]. While the definitions of CT can vary [10], many definitions include the elements: *algorithmic thinking*, *abstraction*, *generalization*,

decomposition, and *evaluation* [10, 11]. Research on holistic CS curricula for ECE that are connected to primary education with a spiral curricula principle is less prominent than empirical research on concrete learning objectives for preschool students according to recent literature reviews [5, 29]. Zeng et al. [29] generated in their literature review an updated CT rubric with classic and emerging CT concepts, practices and perspectives that should be integrated into ECE. These are *control structures*, *representation* and *hardware/software* (for the concepts), *algorithmic design*, *pattern recognition*, *abstraction*, *debugging*, *decomposition*, *iteration*, and *generalization* (for the practices) and lastly *expressing and creating*, *connecting*, *perseverance*, and *choices of conduct* (for the perspectives) [29]. This rubric can be utilized to obtain first ideas for learning objectives of a CT curriculum.

Social demands. CT is according to Wing [27] and other researchers in the field of CT [5, 10] a skill that everybody should learn. Many school curricula worldwide integrated CT in in one way or another [10]. Researchers argue that CT interventions in ECE have longer lasting effects and can be conducted with lower costs (due to more unplugged activities) than later interventions [5]. To reduce the gender bias and foster social participation early on, the integration of CT in ECE seems reasonable [5]. The social demands of Making in ECE have an analogous rationale [26]. Problem decomposition, problem-solving [26] as well as positive technology behaviours such as creativity, communication, collaboration and critical thinking [7] that are part of future skills [19]. The engineering design thinking process is also one common principle between Making and CT [29]. Additionally, both CT and Making in ECE yield the possibility for students to experience first positive technology-related experiences and develop a growth mindset in CS [17]. Additionally to these rationals generated by literature reviews and other studies, our expert group in ECE that consisted of 22 participants from various fields (kindergarten teachers, vocational school teachers, teacher trainers, Making experts, engineers, psychologists and researchers in CS education) agreed that with a cohered focus on the future skills (problem-solving and the four C's) these topics are connected to social demands.

3 Method

This article is based on two studies on the Making and CT intervention that were conducted as well as the new survey with vocational teachers that is presented here. The aim is to generate first empirical insights on Making and CT from various perspectives of the MER-CSE. Overall the data collection consisted of 109 preschool students (62 female, 43 male, 4 missing information; age five to six years old) from seven kindergartens that participated in a nine-week CT intervention, 49 preschool students (27 female, 22 male) from four kindergartens that participated in a nine-week Making intervention, and 22 kindergarten teachers (20 female, 2 male) that conducted the interventions and participated in two 90 minutes online workshops before the interventions and one finale workshop at the end of the interventions (see appendix). None of them had prior knowledge

on CT, Making or CS. Additionally, 14 vocational school teachers (12 female, 2 male) participated in a survey about their prior knowledge on CT and Making. Two teachers already participated in STEM teacher trainings. One teacher knows explanatory patterns for robots and four for drives and electric circuits. Algorithms, CT, programming, Making, and design thinking were completely new to them from a didactical perspective. The questions ask for the definitions of the CS concepts in the context of this study. Thereby assessing conceptions as well as possible challenges as part of the vocational teachers perspectives [17] (see appendix). The data was collected between September 2024 until January 2025. The ethics committee (University of Stuttgart), Ministry of Education Baden-Württemberg approved the study and the teachers, parents, and students gave their informed consent. The sample was acquired via mail to kindergartens and four vocational schools. The observation protocols from the kindergarten teachers and external pre-trained research assistants that had the same protocol guidelines (see appendix) and independently observed on one session as well as the survey results from the vocational school teachers build the data basis for this article. The protocols were analysed to obtain data on challenges, learnings, and instructional approaches from the kindergarten teachers based on the conducted LA. Both were analysed with the thematic analysis according to Brown and Clarke [8]. The interrater agreement between the author and a pre-trained research assistant were between 70% and 97% for the different categories and can be interpreted as fair to almost perfect [9].

3.1 Context of this study

The intervention was developed with twelve experts in ECE [2]. Each LA, lasting 30 to 90 minutes, provided students with opportunities to engage in problem-solving, teamwork, creative design, planning, and critical thinking while developing fine motor skills and becoming familiar with various tools. The LA were grounded in prior research on CT and Making in ECE [13, 28, 7, 26, 5, 29] and discussed at two CS education conferences [1, 2]. All LA are tied together with a storytelling approach. A fictional character "Alex the Bee" was created that the children need to help. The intervention starts with six Making activities described by Bahr [2] and summarized in Figure 2. The LA were designed based of established ECE activities [16, 13, 2] and incorporated design challenges, experimenting, and solving "real-life" problems [15]. The effectiveness of the Making intervention on students' positive technology behaviour was shown by Bahr & Ernst [4] by using the observation rubric from Strawhacker & Bers [25]. Preschool students showed medium to high scores in all six facets *collaboration*, *communication*, *content creation*, *community building*, *creativity*, and *choices of conduct*. No binary gender differences were assessed [4].

The intervention then transitions into CT that is described in details in Bahr [3] and visualized in Figure 3. The learning outcomes added in each LA are described in each column. The effectiveness of the CT intervention analysed with qualitative (the observational scale for CT unplugged activities *OSCTU* from Lin et al. [18]) and quantitative CT assessments (the *TechCheck-K* [21]) was

shown by Bahr [3]. The facets of the CT practices of the *OSCTU* are *algorithms, control structures, representation, debugging, and design process* [18]. The CT concepts of the *TechCheck-K* are *algorithms, control structures, representation, debugging, modularity, and hardware/software*. Thus, the instruments align with the definition of the science content structure outlined in section 2.

Session	LA1	LA2	LA3	LA4	LA5	LA6
Modul	Creating a home	Electrifying the house	Electrify a painting	Creating a city with lights	Creating a brush robot	Creating a friend for the bee
Design thinking concepts	Generate ideas Build empathy Include user perspectives	Maintain/change the product	Generate ideas Build empathy Include user perspectives	Generate ideas Problem framing and defining Experimentation	Generate ideas Prototyping Testing Presenting	Generate ideas Prototyping Testing Presenting
Learning outcomes	use their creativity for creating a home, train their fine motor skills, communicate about various materials	understand and create a simple circuit with a light bulb, understand the difference between closed and open circuits	explain different elements of an electric circuit, use LEDs and copper tape in a circuit, train their planning competences, electrify a painting	develop a deeper understanding of circuits and conductive materials, have fun at making projects	can integrate an electric motor into a circuit, use different tools (e.g., a kids glue gun), create a prototype, explain the principle of imbalance	attach various materials, use design thinking methods for their own project, make use of an engine
Image						

Fig. 2. Overview of the Making intervention with the categorization of Grönman et al. [15], learning outcomes and pictures of the products.

Session	LA7	LA8	LA9	LA10	LA11	LA12	LA13
Modul	Board game	Analogue programming	Sorting buttons	Bee-Bot introduction	Increasingly difficult tasks	Tasks with story	Dance
CT/CS concepts	Abstraction Algorithms	Abstraction Algorithms Decomposition Debugging	Abstraction Sorting Evaluation	Abstraction Algorithms Debugging	Abstraction Algorithms Debugging	Abstraction Algorithms Debugging	Abstraction Algorithms Debugging Generalization
Learning outcomes	understand symbols, communicate commands and form sequences, consider directions, solve first small problems	communicate clear and precise sequences in a different way, understand how robots work	identify characteristics, outliers, logical thinking, collaborate and find agreement	understand symbols of a computing system, understand how a robot (here the Bee-Bot) works	solve increasingly difficult problems	understand new functions of the Bee-Bot (here the pause function) and integrate them into a story	solve a more complex problem, collaborate in a group
Image							

Fig. 3. Overview of the CT intervention ([3], p. 3) with the categorization of Dagiénié et al. [11], learning outcomes and symbols of the learning activities.

4 Results of the Educational Reconstruction of CT and Making in ECE

The results are structured according to the MER-CSE.

Preschool students' perspectives. Difficulties were only observed during the making activities, as many children struggled with fine motor skills. This required additional support from teachers, given that the crafting process is an essential aspect of making and projects should be completed so that the students can experience success. This should be taken into consideration for future making projects in ECE. Students' had also no prior knowledge regarding technology-related content e. g. about electric circuits. As a result, some students caused short circuits in LA5. However, all other LA in making proceeded without issues. According to the observations, students could explain electric circuits, improved their fine motor skills, work with various materials, use prototyping and explain drives.

All teachers stated that the preschool students had no prior experience with CS, CT, or systematic thinking training activities before the intervention. However, all students already had some conception of what a robot is. The teachers attributed this primarily to books and media. Thus, there were no issues during analogue programming (LA8), and the children accurately played the role of a robot, moving according to instructions. According to both the teachers and observations, preschool students had no prior understanding of what algorithms are or what programming entails. It was explained to them that placing a sequence of programming instruction cards (for the board game or the Bee-Bot) was considered programming. Discussions about where to find algorithms in everyday life or how they influence behaviour were not initiated by the teachers. Programming the Bee-Bot, recognizing patterns (e.g., in LA9 with the Bebras task of sorting buttons), identifying and using symbols, and applying decomposition presented no difficulties for the preschool students.

Kindergarten teachers' perspectives. Kindergarten teachers conducted the LA as outlined in section 3.1. During its implementation, they encountered several challenges related to Making, which are detailed below. First, teachers' technology-related knowledge was identified as a key challenge. They experienced difficulties in identifying short circuits created by students, inadvertently caused short circuits themselves, and struggled to provide effective support (e. g., assisting students in screwing a light bulb into a frame). This uncertainty led to unclear instructions, which, in turn, resulted in some students being unsure of how to proceed, ultimately increasing the occurrence of short circuits. These challenges only occurred in LA2 and LA5. LA2 was the first activity with electric circuits and light bulbs. Therefore, the aforementioned challenges were expected. However, at the end of LA2 each student finalized their Making project and achieved the learning outcomes. Defects in the material (crocodile clips, light bulbs or frames) led to teachers and students together searching for the problem and solving it. This was identified as a positive outcome of the intervention by the teachers in the final workshop. Three out of four group of teachers rated LA5 as not age appropriate. The aforementioned challenges mostly occurred in LA5 and the lack of students' fine motor skills paired with the lack of technology-related knowledge led to only some finalized brush robots (two or three out of ten). One group managed to successfully conduct LA5 with the preschool students. Factors

of success identified by the thematic analysis were a step-by-step procedure for the most difficult steps at the beginning of LA5 to complete the prototype (connect brush, batteries, wires and the motor). After this the students could work themselves with little supervision on the brush robot. Besides this, LA1,2,3,4 and 6 were rated as age appropriate after the intervention. Some teachers were surprised that students that usually did not participate that much, were very motivated and engaged during the Making activities. Lastly, teachers identified various sources for materials for students to use in their projects as one key factor for creativity.

Teachers' instruction on CT was clearer compared to the open-ended making projects. No significant difficulties were identified in the qualitative data. The teachers were surprised that the students were already able to solve various CT tasks (LA1) with increasing complexity, such as navigating a grid-based board game with barriers. They noted that LA2 would be a better introduction to CT compared to LA1, as both they and the children were already familiar with some aspects of analogue programming from rhythm-based activities. Additionally, LA1 offers the possibility of increasing difficulty, making it more suitable for the second session rather than the initial introduction. Teachers observed that children immediately began sorting the buttons in LA3 but did not engage in much verbal communication. Therefore, using different buttons with multiple characteristics that encourage more interaction and collaboration should be considered. Regarding the Bee-Bot activities, all teachers agreed that the educational robot was age-appropriate and that the learning activities (LA) effectively engaged students in CT tasks. However, they suggested that LA13, which involved a race, could be omitted from the intervention, as students naturally found the fastest routes themselves and did not express a desire to compete. Furthermore, teachers highlighted that activating students' working memory [23] provided valuable scaffolding and was an effective instructional approach. They also pointed out that external factors, such as depleted Bee-Bot batteries or an uneven mat, led to movement errors and should be taken into account when conducting activities with the robot.

Vocational teachers' perspectives. Regarding the conceptions of teachers about *robots* 30% state that they can be programmed and are a machine or device. 26% highlight that a robot can solve specific tasks and 11% infer that it can reduce workload. One person says that it could look like a human.

Teachers in this sample described an *algorithm* as a step-by-step sequence (19%), that has elementary processing steps (8%), does some kind of data analysis (12%) and solves a task (12%). Furthermore, it has patterns (12%) or loops (12%) and includes a formula (8%). One person each stated that it as something to do with programming, a computer or another system. Lastly, 8% said that it calculated something.

Teachers conceptions of *CT* were either non existent (35%), related to technology-supported thinking, modelling, and programming (each one person), or included some parts of the various definitions of CT such as problem identification, decomposition (each one person), algorithmic thinking (12%), and problem-solving

(24%).

The answers regarding a description of *Making* were doing (37%), crafting or constructing something (32%), nothing (11%), or something related to creativity, digital artifacts, technology, or problem-solving (each one person).

We also asked teachers about *challenges* regarding STEM education at vocational schools. Here the teachers name their content knowledge (32%), didactical knowledge (32%), induction period and time pressure (11%), low self-efficacy (11%), acceptance by the students (11%), and missing appropriate testes teacher materials (one person).

Lastly, we asked teachers about *need of support*. 47% stated need of support regarding didactical knowledge (half of them in general and half regarding programming), 35% regarding teaching materials, and each one person needs support regarding general conditions in vocational schools, pedagogical knowledge, and one in general overall.

5 Discussion

A strong theoretical foundation supports the social demand for integrating Making and CT into ECE [19, 27, 17, 5]. Key aspects such as equity, social participation, and fundamental future skills—albeit in a simplified form—can already be fostered in ECE, forming the rationale for early CT integration (social demands) [20]. Although variations in the definition of CT persist [10] and curriculum development is still in its early stages [17], a broad spectrum of CT concepts, practices, and perspectives is available [5, 29], providing a foundation for structuring CT curricula (science content structure). One key contribution of this study is the aggregation of perspectives from both preschool students and kindergarten teachers, addressing a research gap previously identified [17]. Building on insights from Kim et al. [17], who highlighted the role of teachers in fostering students' growth mindset and social skills, this study further demonstrates that teachers' technology-related competencies significantly influence students' success in Making activities (kindergarten teachers perspectives). Additionally, in contrast to Kim et al. [17], who reported teacher-specific preferences, this study found that teachers followed the provided materials closely without major individual modifications. Teachers did not report significant difficulties in implementing the CT LA. Furthermore, teachers emphasized the effectiveness of the storytelling approach in engaging preschool students, suggesting its potential applicability not only in ECE but also in primary education. Overall, the findings show that in-service kindergarten teachers can integrate CT with the support of a hybrid training (90 min workshop and instructional videos). This work build on the conclusion from Papadakis & Kalogiannakis [20] using unplugged and Bee-Bot activities in the workshop with teachers. Others found that Scratch can be a useful tool to teacher kindergarten teachers [17, 20]. Which approach is more effective can be addressed in future research. The data from vocational school teachers revealed a lack of prior knowledge of CT, Making, and design thinking, highlighting a research gap in integrating these concepts into vocational

education. While none of the vocational school teachers could provide a formal scientific definition of an algorithm or CT, some identified elements of these concepts (vocational school teachers' perspective). Notably, their definitions tended to focus on data analysis, which presents an opportunity for teacher training programs to expand their understanding of algorithms and break down fundamental CT concepts for ECE. Their expressed need for support, particularly in didactical knowledge and teaching materials, further underscores this gap. To our knowledge, no other studies have examined vocational school teachers' perspectives on teaching Making and CT to future kindergarten teachers. Thus, these insights contribute valuable knowledge to the broader discussion on CT in ECE.

5.1 Limitations

The generalizability of the findings is limited in certain aspects. However, the detailed description of the contexts should enable readers to interpret the results in relation to other ECE settings. The LA were developed in collaboration with ECE experts and grounded in prior research, suggesting their applicability to similar contexts. Nevertheless, conceptions of kindergarten teacher education may vary across countries, making the findings from the survey of vocational school teachers not directly transferable to other settings. Furthermore, due to the sample size we can not generalize our findings to all vocational school teachers. The sample size is relatively small, which is common in ECE research [17, 5]. Additionally, data collection primarily relied on kindergarten teachers' observations, rather than direct input from students, which may introduce some limitations. Furthermore, the qualitative analysis of the protocols presents potential constraints. However, this method is generally appropriate for MER-CSE, as similar approaches have been used by other researchers [14].

6 Conclusion

This study generated empirical findings that can now be used to prepare educational content as well as the design and implementation of CT and Making in vocational schools or kindergarten teacher trainings. Next, we want to develop and pilot a course for kindergarten teachers in cooperation with six vocational school teachers and experts in ECE, CT, and Making. Future studies could interview kindergarten teachers and vocational school teachers for more in-depth analysis of the prior knowledge and conceptions further strengthening the empirical basis for the educational reconstruction of CT and Making in ECE.

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7 Appendix

7.1 Survey for vocational school teachers

6.1.1. To what extent are you familiar with the following terms? (6-point Likert scale) I know/can/have...

- ...best practices for teaching
- ...explanation patterns for the term
- ...define the term
- ...partially describe the term
- ...have heard of it before
- ...have not heard of it before

terms: robots, algorithms, programming, CT, making, design thinking, electric circuit, drive.

Open questions:

- 6.1.2 What is your idea of a robot?
- 6.1.3 How would you describe an algorithm?
- 6.1.4 How would you define computational thinking?
- 6.1.5 How would you define making?
- 6.1.6 What challenges do you face in STEM education, i.e., in the elective (mandatory) subject "Research and Experimentation" or in the field of action "Promoting Education and Development I"?
- 6.1.7 What support needs do you identify regarding subject-specific content (computer science, technology), subject-didactic content (support in programming, models of the programming learning process), and pedagogical content?

7.2 Observation protocol for vocational school teachers

Questions before the first implementation:

- 6.2.1 Comfort level with implementing problem-solving (1 = *very low* to 5 = *very high*):
- 6.2.2 Knowledge about problem-solving (1 = very low to 5 = very high):
- 6.2.3 Number of educational professionals for the learning group:
- 6.2.4 Work experience of educational professionals for the preschool learning group and any additional qualifications (e.g., technology educator, project implementation with the "Children Research Foundation"):

Questions after each activity for the implementation log:

The same questions were asked for each LA.

Learning Arrangement 1 (LA1) – Paths in the Preschool (Board Game)

- 6.2.5 Time spent on LA1 (Paths in the Preschool):
- 6.2.6 Date and time of implementation:
- 6.2.7 Brief description of the implementation of LA1:
- 6.2.8 Brief description of difficulties in implementation:

- 6.2.9 Deviations from the "intended" implementation (e.g., aspects that required additional attention for the children):
- 6.2.10 Were there any optional additional activities (e.g., children had already played the algorithm game or other programming-related games)?
- 6.2.11 How would you describe the general atmosphere in the learning group?
- 6.2.12 Were there any special events that influenced the session (e.g., birthdays)?
- 6.2.13 What went particularly well during the implementation?
- 6.2.14 Did the children have difficulties understanding something, problem-solving, or any open questions?
- 6.2.15 To what extent did the children build on knowledge from previous sessions or prior experiences (especially from other STEM-related topics)?
- 6.2.16 How did you address this prior knowledge (e.g., discussing sequences or abstraction)?
- 6.2.17 How varied was the preschool children's prior knowledge?
- 6.2.18 How did you address the differences in prior knowledge among the children?

7.3 Information about the participants

Table 1. Overview of the information about the kindergarten groups including teachers comfort level (CL) in Making and CT as well as their technology-related knowledge (TCK) as well as their experience (in years) as a teacher.

Group	Making	CT	#students	#teachers	CL Making	TCK	CL CT	experience
1	x		17	4	3	2		10 - 35
2	x	x	10	3	3	3	4	1 - 12
3	x	x	15	5	4	4	-	1 - 10
4	x	x	8	2	5	1	4	5 - 15
5		x	24	3			5	2 - 20
6		x	11	5			3	10
7		x	30	3			-	-
8		x	10	1			3	33